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COMBINING LANGUAGES THROUGH COLLABORATIVE INNOVATION

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Abstract

Language is the cultural code of the people. The language in itself represents the embodiment of the ethnic unity, national outlook and the specifics of the people's culture. The study of world languages, the universal human history of human thoughts and feelings must include "all the peoples of the world and all levels of cultural development, in general, everything that belongs to person. The description of the linguistic picture of the world has linguistic importance, because in this way it is possible to reveal and show how the system of means of expression in the language is and how it is worked. ... if this description includes cognitive structures, if it covers the description of the linguistic landscape of the world, the conceptual sphere and concepts, then such a description is linguocognitive and it allows access to a person's information base. Language is an open system, and its characteristics are determined by conceptualization processes related to various areas of human experience.

Language plays main role in the formation of people's ideas about the world, and the results of human understanding of the objective world are recorded precisely in language structures. In addition to the set of knowledge about the world expressed in language, the attitude of a person to the objects of reality is also transformed into the linguistic picture of the world. The linguistic picture of the world is national, and for this reason, it would be more correct to characterize a person as a representative of his nation, respectively, a specific culture. Learning the language is closely related to the conquest of human consciousness and thinking, because language plays a decisive role in relation to human consciousness. Language represents an active, creative beginning in the life of its bearers and forms a certain worldview for it.

Keywords: language innovations, interindividual verbal communication, intersection of communicative spaces

When studying language innovations, that is, language changes, many scientists rely on the linguistic concept of L. V. Shcherba, the theory of speech communication by R. Jakobson, who consider language in the dynamics of interindividual communicative activity in the unity of active processes of speaking (coding) and understanding (decoding). In a given general linguistic context, language is understood as a dynamic system of interindividual verbal communication. The mode of existence of a language is the acts of generation and interpretation of speech contexts unfolding in

time and space by personal codes of linguistic personalities, united in language groups by communicative links and changing in the process of generational change. With this mode of existence, the language, while functioning, is not only reproduced, but necessarily and continuously changes. Therefore, fixing the language in synchrony is a cut of the process of language changes. Language innovations are generated by personal codes and spread through interindividual verbal communication in the language space, becoming

normalized in language communities of different levels, starting from the primary one, for example, the family.

Language contact occurs at the intersection of communicative spaces of two or more languages. Direct language contact exists in the personal codes of bilinguals, but holistically - in speech communication within bilingual communities. The specificity of language contact is most clearly manifested in the interaction of typologically contrasting languages. In these cases, the difference in the mechanisms of language changes that operate in monolingual and bilingual communicative processes becomes significant, first of all, the analogy, which coincides with the principle of language neoplasms in general.[11. p 15]

When bilinguals communicate, the generation and interpretation of innovative language contexts involves not only intralinguistic analogy, but also interlingual analogy. The latter causes linguistic interference and facilitates the decoding of interfered contexts. Borrowed elements of any levels are created in the communicative space of the perceiving language by its systemic means by interlingual analogy and are communicatively distributed through its contexts as its speech units. The degree of significance of language changes is an integral scale for measuring language time, that is, rhythms, cycles, stages of functioning and development of a language. So, for example, whole-system grammatical changes can be interpreted as a transition of the language to a different time. phase or stage, a qualitatively different synchrony.

In the language of every nation there are stable figurative phrases that are produced in speech like a word, and are not built like phrases and sentences. Such turns are called phraseological units. Another important property of phraseology: the meaning of the whole phraseology is not made up of the meanings of the words included in it, for example, the expression "ate a dog", meaning "to be a master in something", is completely unrelated to the meaning of the words included in it.[7,p.70].

Phraseology as a separate and special scientific discipline is formed in middle of the last century. Just a few years after the well-known works of academic Mika V.V. Vinogradov in Soviet linguistics there is a real boom around phraseological issues.

Over the years, various methods of analysis have been created, the most different approaches, based both on the internal semantic features of the phrase-logical units and their external relations. diametrically opposed there were trends laid down by V.V. Vinogradov (the theory of semantic identification) and M.T. Tagiev (the theory of environment). Attempts were made to apply the ideas of structuralism to phraseology. It was assumed that the mathematical accuracy of the analysis would reveal the essence of phraseological semantics in the language.

At present, when cognitivism dominates in linguistics, human factor is put at the forefront in phraseology. This article also presents an attempt to determine the general principles of applying the ideas of cognitivism to the study phraseological material.

It is known that cognition implies the specifics of human cognition. Since cognition refers to thinking in its linguistic embodiment, main language gives the key to the understanding of the ethnic worldview. A person perceives the world through the prism of existing standards.

The main concepts of cognitivism are the concepts of "concept", "mentalness", "conceptualization", "cognitive base", "conceptosphere", national cultural tour space. The term concept means general ideas about objects and phenomena.

V.A. Maslova writes: "Cultural concepts are the names of abstract concepts, therefore cultural information, here it is attached to the significate, i.e. conceptual core" [6, p. 48]. The concept is associated with the significate of the lexical meaning, since it has generalized character.[6.p 47]

The term concept in its modern sense belongs to S.S. Askoldov, who pointed out: "The question of the nature of general concepts or concepts - according to medieval terminology of universals is an old question that has been on the queue for a long time, but almost never touched at its center point. The general concept, as the content of an act of consciousness, remains to this day a very mysterious quantity - an almost imperceptible flicker something in the mental horizon, occurring during rapid pronunciation and understanding of such words as "millennial", "justice", "law", "right" and etc." [1, p. 29]. Therefore, the concept is the most important concept of cognitivism.

In linguistics, the term concept has a new meaning. Concept acts as a philosophical and linguo-cultural category. A. Vezhbitskaya claims that vocabulary is the key to ethnophilosophy, history, and politics. Scholarly decrees- says: "Philosophers, political scientists and jurists usually know that such people are more or less specialized terms like 'bail' [zəmanət], 'warrant' [qarantiya], 'custody' [qəyyumluq], 'solipsism' [solipsizm], 'determinism' [determinizm], 'parliament' [parlament], və 'democracy' [demokratiya], untranslatable. However, much less well known is that the non-special concepts contained in the English words freedom 'freedom', justice 'and truth 'truth; true', are also linguistically specific. Also, the fact that the words of the language encoded certain ways of conceptualizing the world, and not an objective "picture" of the real values, i.e. that the same situation or the same state of affairs for the purposes linguistic coding can be interpreted in different ways" [2, p. 434].

A. Vezhbitskaya believes that in different European languages there are equivalents with this meaning do not mean the same thing. The scientist comes to the conclusion about the need to create semantic meta language, since pseudo-equivalence does not make it possible even to accurately determine the meanings of foreign language equivalents in another language.

In the context of modern anthropocentric linguistics and cognitive linguistics, such concepts as internal form and background information. The term concept means general ideas about objects and phenomena.[2.p. 432]

The term internal form means the literal meaning of the word and phraseological unit.

Cognitive linguistics pays special attention to the nature of the internal form of words and phraseological units, since it is the internal form that reflects the nature of the world concept the mania of the people. Cognitive linguistics pays close attention to research teaching the language as a whole in this aspect, i.e. in terms of differences, in particular, in internal form.

Modern linguistics in the role of cognitive science pays special attention to background information. Background information is usually understood as the totality knowledge, which is not included in the lexical meaning of the word, but without which it is impossible understanding of the text.

Thus, the researchers note that "To the conclusion about the need for moisture communicant, in addition to the language, a set of background knowledge - which is now are defined as mutual knowledge of the realities of the speaker and the listener, which is the basis of linguistic communication, and, consequently, the need to reflect this knowledge in theoretical models of language at different times came many scholars, engaged in the study of human language in all its globality" [7, p. 19]. Here it can be understood as a certain minimum of information behind the language units, and a significant amount of spatio-temporal information.

American linguist Lynn Wisson notes a huge number of errors in English speech of Russian people who live in the USA: "Once I happened to become witnessed a small but very expressive incident at the conference, consisting who appeared in Moscow in the post-perestroika period. When discussing the economic policy of the West and Russia in the new world situation, the American professor abruptly threw Russian colleague: Get your finger out of my face! Indeed, the one to highlight some thought, directed his index finger in his direction, as if confirming Western stereotype of Russians who don't tolerate objections, who are sure that they always and right in everything" [3, p. 186].

Of particular importance in this context is the speech etiquette, under which understand "socially given and culturally specific rules of speech behavior understanding people in situations of communication" [6, p. 47]. Formulas of speech etiquette of different nations not only coincide, but also differ. If the coincidence reflects the general human the eternal essence of etiquette, then national-specific differences are culturally determined fiefs. At the same time, cultural conditioning should be understood not as a simple national specific conditionality, but as a feature of the mentality. [4, p.4]. For example, in the Dictionary of K.E. Hajiyeva "Speech Etiquette of Russians and Azerbaijanis" the most common formulas are given, which reveal a significant difference. So, the greeting formula for a person who has come home from somewhere is quite ordinary: "Welcome! Həmişə evin(-iz)də-əşiyin(-iz)də! Congratulations addressed to a person who has returned from a trip. The Azerbaijani equivalent also expresses the wish not to be away from home for a long time" [4, p. 27].

Linguistics aims to define and explain the national mentality. Apparently, the difference in the forms of expression of national experience means different in the ways of understanding the world around us, which,

in general, means the difference in national characters and stereotypes of behavior. This attitude towards language and understanding of the connection between language and culture makes it absolutely necessary to study in the first place the turn of those language units that directly reflect the history and culture people, their ethnic thinking and psychology. Phraseology is inherently national and cultural in nature, so modern linguistics pays special attention to the study of phraseology, proverbs and sayings, representing ethnic thinking and psychology.

Phraseology in the aspect of cognitivism can be successfully studied at various levels. Of course, in the first place in this series is the study of the mechanism rethinking. If scientists manage to identify the features of the national vision of the world reflected in phraseology, then this can shed light on the specifics of semantic system of the language as a whole. Perhaps the patterns of formation of phraseological semantics in some then the degrees reflect the regularities of the formation of the semantic system of the language.

In other words, it is logical to assume that phraseology, no matter how unique its units seemed to duplicate the general features of the language system in the sphere of national-mental specifics, in particular. On the other hand, the study of phraseology in a cognitive aspect should show what "national specificity" in the language. Perhaps these are just words with no meaning behind them.

The analysis of phraseology at the lexical level will reveal the components that have a cultural tour etymology. It is well known that phraseology at the component level reflects the concepts of national cuisine, clothing, music, architecture, not to mention the well-known fauna and flora. The question is to what extent the component level allows us to assert the national and cultural specificity of phraseology. [12, p 233]

All of the above allows you to understand how relevant in the process of such comparative analysis component, some analysis of phraseological units. Case in the fact that only specific features bearing a national and cultural sign, provide the national and cultural specificity of the phraseological unit as a whole.

One thing is clear, the conceptual basis of phraseology is made up of fragments of linguistic pictures of the world. Consequently, figurative conceptualization of phraseological semantic contains elements of worldview. It follows that the phraseology of any language should be investigated not just at the same level, but at the level of discovery of the connection between the figurative basis and the same organization of the content structure. In this case the organization of the semantic structure of a phraseological unit becomes logical and understandable. [10, p 20-25]

But the explanation of this now understandable organization is entirely consistent with

linguistic picture of the world, which determines the mentality of a particular people. Thus, the structuralist analysis is naturally complemented by the cognitive one.

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